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SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL SURVEY OF ARACHNIDA

SANSA Newsletter 46
SANSA NEWSLETTER

WESTERN CAPE 2022 STATE OF CONSERVATION REPORT

CapeNature's 2022 State of Conservation Report highlights the impressive diversity of invertebrates in the Western Cape and summarises the conservation status of spiders in the province. State of Conservation reports have been produced annually since 2020 and provide updates on the conservation status of species and ecosystems. They also highlight, amongst other things, responses to global biodiversity concerns such as combatting biodiversity crime and protected area expansion. The 2022 report drew on the first ever South African National Red List of Spiders (Foord *et al.* 2020) in conjunction with a Western Cape species list provided by Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. The province supports almost half of all known South African spiders (A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman, pers. comm.), with the Cape Floristic Region being an important spider hotspot with a high degree of endemism. Unfortunately, 3% of the 955 spider taxa in the Western Cape are considered threatened (eight Critically Endangered, nine Endangered, and 10 Vulnerable), mainly because of habitat destruction through urbanisation and agriculture. A copy of the report can be downloaded from the CapeNature website (<https://www.capenature.co.za/news/2023/fresh-from-the-press-2022-state-of-conservation-report>).

REFERENCE

FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., SETHUSA T. & RAIMONDO D. 2020. The South African National Red List of spiders: Patterns, threats, and conservation. *Journal of Arachnology* 48(2): 110–118.

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THE SPIDER COMMUNITY AND THE EFFECTS OF THE FIRE REGIME ON THIS COMMUNITY IN DIVERSE HABITATS OF WELGEVONDEN GAME RESERVE

Congratulations to Greg Canning who obtained his PhD degree in Science, at Tshwane University of Technology in 2023.

ABSTRACT: Fire is a natural disturbance event in savanna systems throughout the world, and in South Africa it is used as a management tool in many protected areas in savanna, and other biomes. It is used to prevent the spread of accidental or natural fires, as a means of removing unwanted and moribund plant material, to create a green flush for grazing wildlife and livestock, as a means of protecting property and as a means of controlling alien and invasive plant species. In many areas the natural fire regime has been altered, limited or even inhibited completely, and this anthropogenic change in the natural fire regime may have unintended consequences for the entire system. On Welgevonden Game Reserve (WGR) in Limpopo Province, fires that are typically lightning strike induced are a regular occurrence. These fires are managed and controlled, to protect both infrastructure and grazing for mammalian wildlife, with little consideration given to the effect that fire has on other taxa.

In this study I assessed the effect that fire has on the spider community of WGR. I used spiders due to their importance as arthropod predators, their use as bioindicators and the lack of knowledge of the spider community on WGR. The study consisted of two parts: sampling of spiders and analyses of variables was carried out from control sampling sites and thereafter from post-fire sampling sites. Control sites were selected based on the vegetation type in both savanna and grassland biomes, with both biomes being managed with disparate fire regimes. In the control sites I sampled spiders to gain baseline knowledge of the spider diversity and to create an annotated species list with information on their conservation status and global distribution. Thereafter I assessed how the frequency of fires and the interval between fires influenced the abundance and diversity of spider communities in these sample sites. I undertook vegetation assessments in the sites and assessed how the fire regime, in conjunction with the vegetation variables, impacted spiders. In the control sites I also assessed the density of ground wandering spiders to determine how this density is affected by fires and used these results to compare to density estimates in post-fire sampling sites.

In the post-fire sampling sites, for a period of a year, I evaluated the recolonisation pathways of spiders into recently burned landscapes. At two post-fire sampling sites I was able to assess how the distance from the edge of a fire influenced the recolonisation of those sites. I then compared the results of the analyses in control sites to the results in post-fire sites to assess how fires affect spider communities. The results of this study, as with numerous others, show that spiders are resilient to fires and that there is a temporal difference in spider communities post-fire event. Although there is a rapid recovery of spider abundance and diversity post-fire events it is however, difficult to predict exactly what pathway that recovery takes as there are differences even within the same vegetation type. Additionally, it is likely that sampling spiders for a year or less, post fire event is unlikely to offer a true reflection of the long-term effects of the fire regime on spider communities.

Sampling at Welgevonden Game Reserve (WGR) in the Limpopo province. Photo: Greg Canning.

FIELD GUIDE TO SCORPIONS OF SOUTH AFRICA

The Field Guide to Scorpions of South Africa is the first comprehensive guide to describe and illustrate all known species in the country. The clear, detailed species accounts cover appearance, habitat and behaviour, and discuss the variation within species according to region. Up-to-date distribution maps are included for all species and exceptional photographs, carefully worked to show astounding detail and vivid colours, bring to life the intricate patterning and colours of different species. Both males and females are presented, as well as a variety of colour forms, facilitating accurate identification in the field.

The introduction discusses scorpion classification, anatomy, biology, behaviour and habitat, as well as venomosity and the treatment of stings. Tips on how and where to find scorpions and how to contribute to their conservation as a citizen scientist are also included. An invaluable tool for students, researchers, academics, hikers, and anyone with an interest in South Africa's rich and fascinating fauna.

Among the world's most fascinating living fossils, scorpions have been around for some 420 million years. South Africa is home to an astonishing variety, with 108 species in three families occurring in most of the region's biomes, from desert and grassland to fynbos, savanna, and forest. Scorpions are even found in urban gardens.

NEW PUBLICATIONS

MAVASA R., YEKWAYO I., MWABVU T. & TSVUURA Z. 2023. Response of ants, beetles and spiders to disturbance varies among taxa in a South African savannah biome. *African Entomology* 31: e13244 (11 pages). <https://doi.org/10.17159/2254-8854/2023/a13244>.

ABSTRACT: Savannahs are structurally complex ecosystems consisting of a diverse community of plants and animals such as arthropods. Arthropods are essential in many ecosystem processes that help maintain life on Earth. The anthropogenic conversion of natural landscapes into croplands and residential and industrial areas has a negative impact on surface-active arthropods that have limited dispersal abilities and narrow habitat preferences. This study investigated the effect of disturbance on assemblages of ants, beetles, and spiders in the savannah vegetation in the Mpumalanga province, South Africa. We compared species richness, abundance, and composition of these three taxa between the pristine savannah and the savannah that is exposed to a variety of anthropogenic activities (disturbed savannah). Arthropods were collected using pitfall traps in 15 sites in pristine savannah and 15 sites in disturbed savannah. We found that disturbance affects species richness and abundance of these taxa differently.

Disturbance did not affect species richness of spiders and abundance of beetles, while greater species richness of ants and beetles, as well as abundance of ants and spiders, was in disturbed than in pristine savannah. Furthermore, the species compositions of all taxa were different between disturbed and pristine savannah. The disturbed savannah had twice more unique indicator species than the pristine savannah. Differences in assemblages of arthropods between pristine and disturbed habitats suggest that it may be important to consider habitats in and outside protected areas in the conservation of arthropods, particularly in areas with a greater percentage of natural and semi-natural landscapes occurring outside protected areas.

SIMBA V., YEKWAYO I. & MWABVU T. 2023. Commercial banana and macadamia plantations in a savanna matrix support high levels of arthropod diversity. *African Entomology* 31: e14047 (9 pages) <https://doi.org/10.17159/2254-8854/2023/a14047>

ABSTRACT: Expansion and intensification of agroecosystems is one of the major causes of habitat loss in the Savanna Biome in South Africa. As such, this study sought to determine the influence of commercial subtropical fruit plantations (banana and macadamia) on species richness, abundance, and composition of surface-active arthropods compared to the Savanna Biome. Given that pesticides and herbicides are applied from spring to early autumn in banana and macadamia plantations, we sampled in winter to reduce the potential impact of pesticides and herbicides. Surface-active arthropods were sampled using pitfall traps. Habitat type did not affect species richness and abundance of ants and spiders, as well as species richness of beetles. However, a significantly greater abundance of beetles was recorded in the macadamia plantation compared to the banana and savanna. This could have been due to greater abundance of herbivorous beetles and other insects, which would have increased the diversity of predatory beetles. Furthermore, unlike the banana plantation, the macadamia plantation was characterised by a deep leaf litter layer and the presence of weeds and grasses, which probably increased the abundance of beetles. Species composition indicated that the studied arthropod taxa associate with specific habitats, as demonstrated by the three habitats supporting different species composition. Despite savanna habitat not supporting high species richness or abundance of surface-active arthropods, we recorded the highest number of unique species of ants and spiders in the savanna rather than in the plantations. These results highlight the importance of natural landscapes in conservation of surface-active arthropods.

Pitfall traps in the macadamia orchard. Photos: Inam Yekwayou.

NEW PUBLICATIONS

BRANDT S., SOLE C. & LYLE R. 2023. Geometric morphometric analysis of ocular patterns as a species identifier in the South African endemic trapdoor spider genus *Stasimopus* Simon, 1892 (Araneae, Mygalomorphae, Stasimopidae). *Evolutionary Biology* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11692-023-09609-0>

ABSTRACT: The identification of *Stasimopus* Simon, 1892 species as well as mygalomorph species has been a long-standing challenge. This is due to their conservative morphologies as well as the lack of quantifiable characteristics. Ocular patterns have historically been used to aid in identification, but have largely been vague and subjective. This study was the first to test for phylogenetic signal in this character to validate its use for species identification and description as well as to test the viability of it in morphospecies and species identification. The results show a significant phylogenetic signal for ocular patterns in both sexes, validating its use. The results display the evolutionary change in ocular patterns across various species. Species and morphospecies show distinct clustering in morphospace, but there is an overlap due to the continuous shape of the character. The methodology of applying geometric morphometrics to quantify ocular patterns can distinguish between morphospecies and shows great promise for distinguishing species.

Stasimopidae *Stasimopus* sp. from the Karoo. Photo: S. Brandt.

BRANDT S., SOLE C. & LYLE R. 2023. The phylogenetic structure and coalescent species delimitation of an endemic trapdoor spider genus, *Stasimopus* (Araneae, Mygalomorphae, Stasimopidae) in the Karoo region of South Africa. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 184 (2023) 107798.

ABSTRACT: The Karoo region of South Africa is a unique and sensitive ecosystem that is facing pressure for development due to economic incentives such as mining, farming, and shale gas exploration. The species diversity of many taxa in the area is largely unknown. A phylogenetic analysis of the cork-lid trapdoor spider genus, *Stasimopus* (Stasimopidae), was undertaken in order to gain insight into the relationships between the species that may be present in the area. The species within *Stasimopus* are challenging to identify and define using traditional morphological methods due to a high degree of morphological conservatism within the genus. For this reason, multiple coalescent-based species delimitation methods were used to attempt to determine the species present for *Stasimopus* in the region, which were tested against the morphological identifications and genetic clades (based on CO1, 16S, and EF-1 γ). We tested single-locus methods Automatic Barcode Gap Discovery (ABGD), Bayesian implementation of Poisson Tree Processes (bPTP), and General Mixed Yule-Coalescent (GMYC), as well as multi-locus Brownie. The phylogenetic analysis of *Stasimopus* in the Karoo showed that there is a high degree of genetic diversity within the genus. The species delimitation results proved unfruitful for the genus, as they appear to delimit population structure rather than species for most methods. Alternative methods should be investigated to aid in the identification of the species in order truly understand the species diversity of the genus.

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Doctoral student graduates making use of the National Collection of Arachnida

Dr Shannon Brandt has recently been awarded her doctoral thesis with the title: 'Under the trapdoor - Resolving the taxonomy and phylogeography of the trapdoor spider of the genus *Stasimopus* (Mygalomorphae: Stasimopidae) of the Karoo.' Dr Brandt's co-supervisor was ARC-PHP staff member, Robin Lyle. Her main supervisor was Dr Catherine Sole from the Department of Zoology and Entomology at the University of Pretoria. This project started as an honours project through the Karoo BioGap project (<https://www.sanbi.org/karoo-biogaps-project/>). Material collected through the work has been deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the ARC-PHP. *Stasimopus* is a genus of cork-lid trapdoor spider under the infraorder Mygalomorphae. The genus is endemic to Southern Africa, but is largely understudied. This study was undertaken to understand the true species diversity and history of this genus in the Karoo region of South Africa. The Karoo is a semi-arid, unique, and sensitive ecosystem that is facing pressure for development due to economic incentives. This area has long been neglected, with few studies investigating the fauna and their phylogeographic history. Part of the project was finding new methods to aid in species identification. Various diagnostic methods were tested against the morphological identifications and monophyletic groupings. The study found that the diversity of the genus is significantly higher than previously believed, including the description of nine new species. The final data chapter unravelled the phylogeographic patterns of the genus in the Karoo. The study highlights the large number of short-range endemics present in the Karoo, which are of great conservation concern.

Shannon Brandt graduating with her supervisors Robin Lyle (ARC, on the left) and Dr Catherine Sole (UP, on the right).

WILD DOGS FEEDING ON *STEGODYPHUS* SPIDERS IN KRUGER PARK

We were travelling in October 2020 on the road from Shimuwini to Mopani in the Kruger National Park near the Phalaborwa - Mopani connection when we observed this interesting behaviour of a group of wild dogs. A group of wild dogs were playing around when they discovered small nests of community-nest spiders attached to branches of young mopani trees (Fig. 1). Amazingly they had to jump to pull the nests from the trees (Fig. 2). They first feasted on the nest lower down before focusing on the nest higher up. Sometimes they had to jump really high up to be able to get to the nest (Figs 3-4). As the nest was pulled down, they would join in feeding on it. They carried on until all the nests in that area were removed.

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Figures 1-5. Wild dogs in the Kruger National Park feeding on *Stegodyphus*. Photos: Anso le Roux

SAVE THE DATE

Colloquium
of the African
Arachnological
Society

14TH

Date: 28 January – 1 February 2024

Venue: ATKV Buffelspoort, Rustenburg

Website: <https://buffelspoort.co.za/home/>

*Join us in celebrating
arachnological research in Africa!*

*Hosted by the ARC – Plant Health
& Protection, Arachnology Unit*

More information to be shared shortly.

Please feel free to email Robin Lyle at LyleR@arc.agric.za to be added to the mailing list.

RECENT PUBLICATIONS

BRANDT S., SOLE C. & LYLE R. 2023. The phylogenetic structure and coalescent species delimitation of an endemic trapdoor spider genus, *Stasimopus* (Araneae, Mygalomorphae, Stasimopidae) in the Karoo region of South Africa. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 184 (2023) 107798.

BRANDT S., SOLE C. & LYLE R. 2023. Geometric morphometric analysis of ocular patterns as a species identifier in the South African endemic trapdoor spider genus *Stasimopus* Simon, 1892 (Araneae, Mygalomorphae, Stasimopidae). *Evolutionary Biology* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11692-023-09609-0>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831547>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2023. *The Bemmeridae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 41 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7810486.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN ZYL J. 2023. First record of the trash-line spider *Cyclosa conica* (Pallas, 1772) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 45(2023): 13–14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828887>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2023. First record of the crab spider *Diaea longisetosa* Roewer, 1961 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 15–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831492>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L., & STEENKAMP R. 2023. First record of the crab spider *Diaea albicincta* Pavesi, 1883 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 17–18. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828983>.

MAVASA R., YEKWAYO I., MWABVU T. & TSVUURA Z. 2023. Response of ants, beetles and spiders to disturbance varies among taxa in a South African savannah biome. *African Entomology* 2023, 31: e13244 (11 pages). <https://doi.org/10.17159/2254-8854/2023/a13244>.

PELSER D., HERON H., & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. The male of the spiny-back orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 11–12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828868>.

SIMBA V., YEKWAYO I. & MWABVU T. 2023. Commercial banana and macadamia plantations in a savanna matrix support high levels of arthropod diversity. *African Entomology* 2023, 31: e14047 (9 pages) <https://doi.org/10.17159/2254-8854/2023/a14047>.

WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Jeffreys Bay, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831510>

SPIDERS OF FERNKLOOF NATURE RESERVE

The new spider book will be launched on
23 September 2023 at the Flower Show
in Hermanus

For more information contact Victor Hamilton-Attwell
at vicattwell@sonicmail.co.za

Notes on the crab spider *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Linda Wiese², Karen Pagel³ & Jolandie Buck⁴

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Abstract: The male of *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883 was the first time recorded from Caffraria, South Africa. During surveys in the Eastern Cape, a female was the first time sampled with a male. The general morphology of both sexes of the species is described and photographs of live specimens provided and notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation are provided.

Keywords: behaviour, biodiversity, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large areas in South Africa were surveyed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and numerous Thomisidae sampled. The second author (LW) sampled some strange thomisids from the Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020) that were eventually identified as *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883.

The genus *Phaenopoma*, an African endemic genus, is poorly known and presently known only from three species (World Spider Catalog, 2023). Members of *Phaenopoma* are characterised by their very flattened bodies, resembling members of the genus *Firmicus*, but the eye pattern and genitalia differ. Unfortunately the specimens lose their colour when placed in alcohol.

Phaenopoma nigropunctatum, the type species, is a South African endemic species that was described from a male by O. Pickard-Cambridge (1883) as *Nesis nigropunctatus*. The type locality was only listed as Caffraria, South Africa. The other two known species (*P. milloti* Roewer, 1961, from Senegal and *P. planum* Simon, 1895, from Sierra Leone) are based on immature specimens.

In the present paper we provide the first images of live specimens. The male is redescribed and the female described for the first time. New distribution records for the species are added, as well as notes of their behaviour and conservation status.

METHODS

For the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), photographs of South African species were requested to obtain additional information on their morphology and distribution. The second author (LW) photographed the male and female in the Addo National Park, in the Eastern Cape and the third author (KP) provided photographs from Natures Valley in the Western Cape and the fourth author (JB) provided photos from Gondwana Private Nature Reserve.

Voucher specimens sampled during the SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria.

TAXONOMY

Phaenopoma nigropunctatum (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883)

Nesis nigropunctatus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883: 361.

Phaenopoma nigropunctata Simon, 1895: 983; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020b: 34.

Figures 1–2. *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum*. 1. Male from Addo National Park, dorsal view. 2. Female from Addo National Park, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1–2. Linda Wiese.

Diagnostic characteristics: Male: (Figs 1 & 3–6). Size: TL 3–4 mm. Carapace, abdomen, and legs reddish brown in live specimens (colour fades in alcohol); abdomen ventrally a paler duller brown (Fig. 13); carapace with narrow dark marginal band (Fig. 3); palp dark; abdomen lateral border decorated with a row of small black spots (Figs 1, 3, 14, 15). Carapace as long as wide; truncated in front, constricted laterally at the margins; upper surface flat and level; eyes small and slightly different in size, occupying the whole width of carapace (Figs 6–7); both eye rows recurved, four median eyes smallest; anterior lateral eyes larger than posterior lateral eyes; lateral eyes situated on small tubercles; maxillae long, enlarged at the extremities, where they are obliquely and slightly roundly truncated on the outer side; labium more than half the length of the maxillae, constricted laterally near the middle; sternum oval, truncated anteriorly and pointed posteriorly (Fig. 13). Abdomen oblong, truncated anteriorly, and pointed posteriorly; very flat (Figs 11–12); sometimes abdomen posterior tip with short dark lines. Legs: front legs darker than carapace; first and second pairs longest; armed with a few paired slender spines beneath the tibiae and metatarsi of the first and second pair of legs; tarsal claws with small claw-tuft. Palpi large, dark brown with a strong retrotibial apophysis, with apex pointed and tip slightly twisted; cymbium with swollen lateral area; embolus medium length curved once around tegulum (Figs 8–9).

Females (Fig. 2) resemble males in general shape and size but are less flattened. In live specimen carapace and legs bright green with chelicerae and palpi pale brown. Abdomen fawn; dorsally decorated with 10–12 small black spots on lateral border and five pairs of green spots varying in size mediolaterally. Epigyne: atrium with U-shaped border (Fig. 10).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park (-33.88, 26.45), 1m, 1f (NCA 2011/1282); Alexandria State Forest (-33.705, 26.368), 1m (NCA 99/366); Paterson (-33.440, 25.968, 2m, 6 imm (NCA 2007/2078); The Haven, Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.240, 28.911), 3m, 1 imm (NCA 2007/329); East London (-33.01, 27.90), 1m (NCA 77/1089); Gonubie Beach (-32.933, 28.0167), 1m (NCA 77/1213); Grahamstown (-33.306, 26.525), 1m (NCA 88/498); Hogsback, Amatola Mts. (-32.594, 26.944), 1m (NCA 2014/466), same locality data, 1m (NCA 2014/493); Kei Mouth (-32.687, 28.374), 1m (NCA 2004/304); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89), 2f (NCA 88/495); Sundays River Valley (-33.39, 25.43), 1m (2007/2078); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.981, 23.559), 1 imm (NCA 79/84, 86/37). **KwaZulu-Natal:** 1.5 km E of Mtunzini Umlazi Nature Reserve (-29.95, 30.86), 1m (Natal Museum 12328); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-27.00, 32.83), 1m (NCA 2000/437). **Western Cape:** Natures Valley (-33.97, 23.57), 1m (photo); Gondwana Nature Reserve (-34.18, 22.12) (photo).

LIFESTYLE

They are free-living plant-dwellers. The males were very agile and moved around on the vegetation (Figs 13–15). Most of the specimens were sampled mainly by hand and sweep netting from vegetation in the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Thicket, and Savanna biomes.

Figures 3–12. *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum*. 3–4. Male from Addo National Park (in alcohol). 5. Line drawing of male. 6–7. Eye pattern. 8–9. Male palp. 10. Epigyne. 11–12. Male. Photo credits: 5, 6, 9. After O. Pickard-Cambridge (1883). 11–12. Karen Pagel. 3, 4, 7, 8, 10. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

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Figures 13–15. *Phaeopoma nigropunctatum* male observed in low vegetation at the Gondwana Private Game Reserve. Photo credits: Jolandie Buck.

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CONSERVATION

The species is mainly known from the Eastern Cape, with a few records from the Western Cape and KwaZulu-Natal. The species is protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020), Gondwana Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Buck 2023), Alexander State Forest, Cwebe Nature Reserve, Tsitsikamma National Park, and Umlazi Nature Reserve. Due to wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank Rudi Steenkamp for his assistance in obtaining the photographs.

More on the spotted jumping spider *Thyene coccineovittata* (Simon, 1886) in South Africa (Araneae: Salticidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Peter Webb²

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Abstract: The spotted jumping spider *Thyene coccineovittata* (Simon, 1886) has a wide distribution in Africa and is known from the Ivory Coast to South Africa. The species was also accidentally introduced in France and Brazil. The general morphology of both sexes of the species is discussed, with photographs of live specimens and notes on their behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont, behaviour, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Thyene* Simon, 1886 is represented by 52 species and subspecies, with 14 species recorded from South Africa. Most of the *Thyene* species can be distinguished by their colouration and the presence of tufts of long black hairs near the posterior median eyes.

Thyene coccineovittata (Simon, 1886) is a species of African origin described from Senegal as *Hyllus coccineovittatus*. The species has a wide distribution throughout Africa and is known from the Ivory Coast to South Africa. The species was also accidentally introduced in France (Oger & Van Keer, 2017) and Brazil (Mariante & Hill, 2018).

The aim of this paper is to provide more information on the morphology of both sexes based on live specimens, their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa, with notes on their agrobiont status.

TAXONOMY

Thyene coccineovittata (Simon, 1886)

Hyllus coccineovittatus Simon, 1886: 348.

Thyene crudelis: Peckham & Peckham, 1903: 229; Berland & Millot, 1941: 371.

Thyene coccineovittata: Berland & Millot, 1941: 371, 373; Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009: 83.

Diagnostic characteristics: The species was redescribed by Wesolowska and Haddad (2009) with detailed drawings. The live male can be recognised by the rounded reddish-brown carapace, with darker margins and eyes surrounded by black rings and short whitish setae forming poorly contrasted bands: one on middle of thoracic part and two on carapace sides, near the eye field; tufts of long brown bristles form 'horns' at posterior median eyes. The abdomen dark, brownish-fawn, with lighter shiny streak along middle; two pairs of very small, but clearly contrasted white marks posteriorly; venter dark, with two lines composed of white dots (Figs 4–6). Male palp with tibial apophysis very short, tegulum rounded, embolus very long, encircling the tegulum five times (Figs 7–9).

Female: smaller than male; carapace orange-brownish, eye field tinged with grey, eyes circled by black; around anterior median eyes row of white scales; sparse brown and white setae on carapace, tufts of long bristles near posterior median eyes. Abdomen with several lines anteriorly, in posterior two-thirds of its length with three pairs of large blackish patches (Figs 1–3). Legs dark yellow, with brown hairs and spines; first legs thickest, femora I and II thin black stripes on anterolateral side; tibiae short and slightly swollen; metatarsi short; first tibia with three pairs of ventral spines, metatarsus with two pairs; pedipalps pale. Female epigyne typical for *Thyene*, weakly sclerotised, with rectangular depression anteriorly (Figs 10–11).

Figures 1–3. *Thyene coccineovittata* female. Photo credits: 1–2. Peter Webb. 3. After Wesolowska and Haddad (2009).

Figures 4–6. *Thyene coccineovittata* male. Photo credits: 4. Vida vd Walt. 5. Peter Webb. 6. After Wesolowska and Haddad (2009).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Mali, Senegal, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Kenya, South Africa. Introduced to France and Brazil.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Keurkloof district, Ferndale Farm (-33.68, 24.83); Tsolwana Nature Reserve (-32.17, 26.50). **Free State:** Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.50, 28.62). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Greytown (-29.05, 30.60); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngotsche district, Vergeval Farm (-27.35, 31.61); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Luvhondo Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Maasroom (-22.75, 28.43); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Swadini Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.2, 30.34). **Mpumalanga:** Burger's Hall (-32.02, 31.08); Marble Hall (-25.09, 29.09); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit district, Brondal Farm (-25.35, 30.84); Nelspruit district, Glenwood Farm (-29.87, 30.98); Schagen (-25.43, 30.80); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Western Cape:** Citrusdal (-32.59, 19.02); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-23.67, 28.38); Camps Bay (-33.95, 18.37).

Figures 7–11: *Thyene coccineovittata*. 7–9 Male palp. 10–11. Epigyne. Credits: 8, 9, 11. After Wesolowska and Haddad (2009). 7 & 10. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Figure 12. Known distribution of *Thyene coccineovittata* in South Africa.

LIFE STYLE

Thyene coccineovittata is commonly found on vegetation and sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011), and Thicket biomes.

The species was identified as an agrobiont species after it was collected from several agroecosystems (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) such as avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), citrus (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1998), macadamia (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001), and grapefruit orchards in South Africa.

In the macadamia orchards spiders were collected over a 12-month period (July 1997–June 1998) from three macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa using dichlorvos as a knock-down spray (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001). Of the 2 778 spiders collected, 2020, 73% belonged to the Salticidae represented by 17 species with *T. coccineovittata* the most abundant species. It represented 30% of all the spiders collected.

Figure 13. Seasonal fluctuation of *Thyene coccineovittata* in macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld, South Africa (After Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001).

Males, females, and juveniles were collected throughout the year in roughly comparable numbers, viz. females (32%) males (29%), and juveniles (39%) (Fig. 13). The males peaked in September and February. The number of males declined to a low in May and June and females in July. The most juveniles were recorded in April.

In the avocado orchards *T. coccineovittata* were present in lower numbers with Salticidae representing 31% of all specimens collected. The 426 *T. coccineovittata* sampled represented 11.6% of the total salticid sampled.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has been sampled from several protected areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 2003), and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016).

In Brazil, *T. coccineovittata* was recorded mainly in urban vegetation (Mariane & Hill, 2018). This may indicate that the species prefers environments such as gardens, urban parks, woods, and forests in Brazil. If the species starts to occupy natural niches, it could pose a threat to arthropod populations and their ecosystem relationships. However, more studies are needed on its invasive potential and its impact on ecosystems.

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Additional information on the brown crab spider *Thomisus scrupeus* (Simon, 1886) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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Abstract: *Thomisus scrupeus* (Simon, 1886) has been recorded throughout Africa. The presence of *T. scrupeus* in South Africa is discussed, with notes on their colour variation and morphology based on live photographs. Information on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation in South Africa is provided.

Keywords: behaviour, biodiversity, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), large numbers of specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). This includes several *Thomisus* specimens of which one was identified as *T. scrupeus* (Simon, 1886). *Thomisus scrupeus* was described by Simon (1886) from Senegal as *Daradius scrupeus*. It is widespread throughout Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2023).

The brown crab spider differs from other African *Thomisus* species by having a granular integument, and a body covered with small polyp-like tubercles and the two pairs of front legs with thickened patellae and tibiae giving it a robust appearance. The body colour varies in the female from off-white to yellow orange to dark brown in the male. Body shape and colour vary greatly between the sexes (Figs 1–2) as well as specimens of the same sex (Figs 11–16). The body shape also varies, with the abdomen flattened (Fig. 5) to more prominent tubercles on abdomen (Fig. 15) to more rounded (Fig. 11). The variation in shape and colour have resulted in several synonyms of *T. scrupeus* such as *Thomisus caffer* Simon, 1904, *T. amanicus* Strand, 1907, *T. quadrituberculatus* Lessert, 1943, and *T. lindneri* Roewer, 1956 (World Spider Catalog, 2023).

The objective of this study is to show the variation in shape and colour based on photographs of live specimens, and the general behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa are discussed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens examined are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria.

As part of SANSa, requests were made for photographs for the SANSa Virtual Museum and several were received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Thomisus scrupeus (Simon, 1886)

Daradius scrupeus Simon, 1886: 363

Thomisus scrupeus Comellini, 1957: 26; Jézéquel, 1964:

1121; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 17; 1988: 432; 2020: 57–58.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL females 7–8 mm, males 3–5 mm. This species differs from other species by having a granular integument, a body covered with small polyp-like tubercles (Fig. 5), and two pairs of robust front legs with thickened patellae and tibiae (Fig. 4). Female: carapace wider than long; eye tubercles flattened dorsally, sharply pointed; (Fig. 3) both eye rows recurved. Abdomen bell-shaped, usually with dark brown band between abdominal tubercles (Figs 1 & 12). Legs: legs I and II robust; with femora, tibiae, and metatarsi thickened; tibiae I and II with 3–4 pairs of short and thick macro-setae. Epigyne simple, U-shaped (Fig. 6). Male: structurally very similar to female, differs as follows: smaller; body more flattened (Fig. 2); abdomen without prominent tubercles on abdomen; macrosetae longer on tibiae and metatarsi of legs I and II. Palp: large with strong retrolateral apophysis; embolus short (Fig. 7).

Figure 1–2. *Thomisus scrupeus* 1. Female. 2. Male. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 3–8: *Thomisus scrupeus*. 3. Eye pattern. 4. Leg I. 5. Polyp with body setae. 6. Epigyne. 7–8. Male palp. Photo credits: 3. Peter Webb. 4–7 After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Widespread throughout Africa. Recorded from Senegal, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Malawi, Rwanda, South Africa, Tanzania, Zaire, and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Fort Grey (-33.19, 27.12); Grahamstown, Gretna Farm (-33.3, 26.52); Idutywa (-32.1, 28.3); Kentani (-32.5, 28.32); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis (-34.206, 24.708); Jeffreys Bay (-34.06, 24.91). **Gauteng:** Cullinan Premier Game Farm (-25.67, 28.48); Moloto, Farm Enkeldoorn (-25.46, 28.63); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Roodeplaa Dam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Irene (Smuts House) (-25.89, 28.23); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19).

KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56); Lake Sibayi (-27.33, 32.68); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Shaka's Rock (-29.49, 31.24); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57); Zululand, Manguzi forest (-28.33, 31.08); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.54, 32.15); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.034, 32.425). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park, Shabenikop, 5 km N Pretoriuskop (-22.93, 31.02); Maastroom, Farm Swellendam (-22.75, 28.43); Makalali Private Game Reserve, Pidwa (-24.16, 30.69); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38); Zanzibar Border Post (-22.57, 28.45); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Delmas (-26.14, 28.68); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Witrivier (-25.31, 31.02). **North West:** Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.62, 27.77); Hartbeespoort dam (-25.73, 27.85); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

Western Cape: Diepwalle Forest Station (-34.03, 23.03); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Gouritsmond (-34.34, 21.87); Saasveld Forest Station (-33.95, 22.53); Wilderness (-33.99, 22.59).

Figure 9. Known distribution of *Thomisus scrupeus* in South Africa.

Figures 10–12. *Thomisus scrupeus* female. 9. Female in retreat. 10. Female on egg sac. 11. Female with spiderlings. Photo credits: 10. J. Munton-Jackson. 11-12. Peter Webb.

Female from Irene, Gauteng

Female from Bronkhorstspuit, Gauteng

Female from Irene, Gauteng

Female from Addo Elephant National Park

Female from Nwandeni, Limpopo

Female from Lephahlale, Limpopo

Male from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal

Male from Irene, Gauteng

Male from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal

Figures 11–19. *Thomisus scrupeus*. 11–16. Females. 17–19. Males. Photo credits: Peter Webb, except 14. Linda Wiese.

LIFESTYLE

Thomisus scrupeus was frequently sampled during SANSA surveys mainly while beating or sweeping vegetation. They are free-living plant dwellers and appear to be largely restricted to the shrub and tree layer. Field observations showed that the species is much more abundant in the summer months. Adult females have been sampled from December to May and males from November to January (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983).

The female attaches the white egg sac to a slightly curved leaf and she stays with her egg sac until the spiderlings hatch and the spiderlings are strong enough to disperse (Figs 10–12). They are frequently observed holding their front legs together as shown in Figs 22 & 23.

At the Ndumo Game Reserve, *T. scrupeus* was mainly sampled from broadleaf woodland, *Vachellia tortilis* savanna, and *V. xanthophloea* forests (Haddad *et al.*, 2006). It was also sampled in the Blouberg Nature Reserve from *Sclerocarya birrea* (Muelwala *et al.*, 2010). In orchards it was sampled in avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005) and citrus (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Figures 20–21. *Thomisus scrupeus* showing the typical position of the legs. Photo credits: 22. Ruan Booysen. 3. Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION STATUS

Thomisus scrupeus has a wide global distribution and is listed as Least Concern. In South Africa it is protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al., 2006); Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al., 2010); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2011); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al., 2016); Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2020); Marakele National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2021); Thyspunt (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2022), and Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

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A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Gondwana Private Game Reserve, in the Western Cape, South Africa

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Abstract: This paper provides the first annotated species list of spiders presently known from Gondwana Private Game Reserve, a reserve recognised as a Cape Floral World Heritage Site in the Western Cape. A total of 148 species from 106 genera and 33 families were recorded and photographed. The most species-rich families are the Araneidae (32 spp.), Thomisidae (20 spp.) and Salticidae (17 spp.). Several species are possibly new to science. The conservation status and level of endemism, based on their known distribution, are provided for each species.

Keywords: conservation, endemism, Fynbos Biome, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The Gondwana Private Game Reserve (GPGR) is situated on the south-western border of the Western Cape, South Africa, approximately 30 km from Mossel Bay. The reserve is recognised as a Cape Floral World Heritage Site in the Fynbos Biome. Despite the relatively small extent of coverage of the biome, about 6.7% in South Africa, it is regarded as a priority hotspot for conservation (Goldblatt, 1997).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), several surveys have been undertaken in the Fynbos Biome and presently a total of 466 localities have been sampled in this biome, with >11 000 specimens recorded. Presently, 67 spider families represented by 1 014 spp. are known from the biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). To date, only a few studies have been published that focus on fynbos spider diversity: the Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009); Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2016); Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021), and Thyspunt (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2022).

Here we report on a survey that was undertaken in the GPGR with the aim to determine the spider diversity and to photograph all the species to generate the first species checklist. The conservation status and level of endemism of each species sampled are provided that can serve as a reference for future studies in the Fynbos Biome.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: The GPGR covers 11 000 ha and is situated at the foot of the Langeberg mountains in the Western Cape province, South Africa (-34.089, 21.912) (Fig. 4). It is a core conservation area in the Fynbos Biome and it receives 400–690 mm of rainfall annually for the years 2017–2022. The vegetation can broadly be classified as fynbos (Figs 1–2), old pasturelands (grasslands) (Fig. 3), shale renosterveld, indigenous thickets, and invasive alien forests (black wattle).

Collecting methods: The Gondwana Conservation Foundation or GCF (under leadership of second author) is presently busy with surveys to determine the biodiversity of the fauna and flora of the reserve. Surveys are done through vegetation sweeps and *ad hoc* observations of species found on the vegetation. Specimens are collected, photographed, and released. Images are housed in iNaturalist (697 records). Identifications of species listed here were made by the first author.

Figure 1. Gondwana Game Reserve mixed fynbos. Photo credit: Jolandie Buck.

Figure 2. Gondwana Game Reserve wetland. Photo credit: Jolandie Buck.

Figure 3. Gondwana Game Reserve grassland. Photo credit: Jolandie Buck.

Figure 4. Map showing location of the Gondwana Private Game Reserve in the Western Cape.

The checklist includes additional species that were previously sampled from GPGR and now housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

Endemicity value: The indices to assess the endemicity value and conservation status of each species are: 6—species only known from the type locality (GGR); 5—species known only from the Western Cape, a Western Cape endemic (WCE); 4—species known from the Western Cape and an adjoining province; 3—known from >three provinces, a South African endemic (SAE); 2—known from other countries in Southern Africa (STHE); 1—known from several countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE); 0—also from outside the Afrotropical Region (Foord *et al.*, 2020).

Conservation status: This value was determined for each species from a recent Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020).

- LC: least concern, when species has a wide distribution;
- DD: data deficient, through either a lack of distribution data or taxonomic resources;
- NE: species not evaluated because they are immature or those that represent possible new species or undetermined taxa.
- EN: endangered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 148 species in 106 genera and 33 families were recorded (Table 1; Appendix 1). Sixteen species could not be identified to species level as some specimens were immature and some were possibly new species or new records of species to South Africa (Appendix 1). The number of species collected compares well with other fynbos surveys, e.g. the Swartberg Nature Reserve, where 186 species were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005) and 184 species from the Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

Of the 33 spider families collected from GPGR (Table 1; Appendix 1), the Araneidae (32 spp.), Thomisidae (20 spp.) and the Salticidae (17 spp.) were the most species-rich, while 14 families were only represented by a single species.

Conservation status: Of the 148 species sampled, 7 spp. (4.7%) are data deficient (DD), i.e., lacking taxonomic or distribution data. The majority of the species (124 spp., 83.8%) are listed as least concern (LC). They have a wide distribution with 61.5% of the species also known outside South Africa (Table 2). Seventeen of the species were not evaluated (NE), seven were immature, and ten may be new to science (Figs 6–12). Only one species, *Diores dowsetti* Jocqué, 1990 (Zodariidae), is listed as endangered due to the species having a small restricted distribution range (<5 000 km²).

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Gondwana Private Game Reserve with the total number of families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.).

FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.	FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.
Amaurobiidae	2	2	Palpimanidae	1	1
Araneidae	20	32	Philodromidae	3	3
Bemmeridae	1	1	Phyxelididae	2	2
Caponiidae	1	1	Pisauridae	4	5
Cheiracanthiidae	2	2	Salticidae	11	17
Clubionidae	1	2	Scytodidae	1	1
Corinnidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	2
Ctenidae	1	1	Sparassidae	3	5
Deinopidae	1	1	Stasimopidae	1	1
Desidae	1	1	Tetragnathidae	2	3
Dictynidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	2	3
Eresidae	2	2	Theridiidae	10	11
Gallieniellidae	1	1	Thomisidae	12	20
Gnaphosidae	3	3	Trachelidae	1	1
Hahniidae	1	1	Zodariidae	3	4
Lycosidae	7	8	Zoropsidae	1	1
Oxyopidae	2	8		106	148

Species endemicity: A large percentage of species (49 spp., 33.1%) have a wide distribution throughout Africa, while 17 spp. (11.5%) are also found wider than Africa. A total of 25 spp. (16.9%) are endemics to Southern Africa, and only 57 spp. (38.5%) are South African endemics.

There are presently 15 of the GPGR species endemic to the Western Cape and 12 near endemics, but at this stage no species are endemic to the reserve. However, some of the 16 species not evaluated might be new to science.

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemicity of the spider species sampled at the Gondwana Private Game Reserve.

DISTRIBUTION	SPP.	%
CONSERVATION STATUS		
DD data deficient	7	4.7
LC least concern	123	83.2
NE not evaluated	17	11.4
EN Endangered	1	0.7
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	17	11.5
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	49	33.1
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	25	16.9
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	15	10.1
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	12	8.1
5 –Western Cape endemics (WCE)	14	9.5
6 – Gondwana Private Game Reserve (GPGR)	0	0

CONCLUSION

This survey contributes to our knowledge on the geographical distribution of spider species in the Fynbos Biome. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Figures 5–12. Undetermined species from Gondwana Private Game Reserve. 5–8. Araneidae species. 9. New Philodromidae genus. 10. Undescribed *Oxyopes* sp. 11. Theridiidae sp. 1 cf. *Spinembolia*. 12. Theridiidae *Rubroridion* sp. new. Photo credits: Jolandie Buck.

Figures 12–26. Species from Gondwana Private Game Reserve. 12–19 Araneidae spp. 12. *Isoxya semiflava*. 13. *Araneus coccinella*. 14. *Gasteracantha sanguinolenta*. 15. *Pycnacantha tribulus*. 16. *Neoscona hirta*. 17. *Argiope trifasciata*. 18. *Cyclosa insulana*. 19. *Gea infuscata*. 20. *Gandanameno fumosa* (Eresidae). 21. *Caponia capensis* (Caponiidae). 22. *Aphantaulex stationis* (Gnaphosidae). 23. *Drassodella quinquelabecula* (Gallieniellidae). 24. *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* (Thomisidae). 25. *Thyene bucculenta* (Salticidae). 26. *Rhene capensis* (Salticidae). Photo credits: Jolandie Buck.

Fig-

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Gondwana Private Game Reserve (GPGR) listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), and country endemism (CEND).

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
AMAUROBIIDAE	<i>Chresiona</i> sp. immature		NE	
	<i>Chumma gastroperforata</i> Jocqué, 2001	4	LC	SAE
ARANEIDAE	<i>Arachnura scorpionoides</i> Vinson, 1863	1	LC	AE
	<i>Araneus coccinella</i> Pocock, 1898 (Fig. 12)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Araneus haploscapella</i> (Strand, 1907)	3	DD	SAE
	<i>Araneus nigroquadratus</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775) (Fig. 17)	0	LC	C
	<i>Caerostris corticosa</i> Pocock, 1902	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Caerostris sexcupidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834) (Fig. 18)	0	LC	C
	<i>Cyclosa oculata</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	0	LC	C
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844 (Fig. 14)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Gea infuscata</i> Tullgren, 1910 (Fig. 19)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hypsacantha crucimaculata</i> (Dahl, 1914)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Isoxya semiflava</i> Simon, 1887 (Fig. 12)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinia natalensis</i> (Grasshoff, 1971)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844) (Fig. 16)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	0	LC	C
	<i>Neoscona novella</i> (Simon, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C
	<i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Paraplectana</i> sp. immature			NE
	<i>Poltys</i> sp. immature			NE
	<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781) (Fig. 15)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zygiella x-notata</i> (Clerck, 1757)	0	LC	C	
Araneidae sp. 1 (undetermined new?) (Figs 5–6)			NE	
Araneidae sp. 2 (undetermined new?) (Figs 7–8)			NE	
BEMMERIDAE	<i>Homostola reticulata</i> (Purcell, 1902)	5	DD	SAE
CAPONIIDAE	<i>Caponia capensis</i> Purcell, 1904 (Fig. 21)	2	LC	STHE
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona clavigera</i> (Simon, 1897)	3	LC	SAE
CLUBIONIDAE	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
	<i>Clubiona</i> sp. immature			NE
CORINNIDAE	<i>Apochinomma</i> sp. new			NE
CTENIDAE	<i>Ctenus parvoculatus</i> Benoit, 1979	3	LC	SAE
DEINOPIIDAE	<i>Menneus capensis</i> (Purcell, 1904)	5	LC	SAE
DESIDAE	<i>Badumna longinqua</i> (L. Koch, 1867)	0	LC	C
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Shango capicola</i> (Strand, 1909)	5	DD	SAE
ERESIDAE	<i>Gandanameno fumosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837) (Fig. 20)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Stegodyphus mimosarum</i> Pavesi, 1883	1	LC	AE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
GALLIENIELLIDAE	<i>Drassodella quinquelabecula</i> Tucker, 1923 (Fig. 23)	5	LC	SAE
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Aphantaulax stationis</i> Tucker, 1923 (Fig. 22)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pterotricha auris</i> (Tucker, 1923)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Scotophaeus relegatus</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
HAHNIIDAE	<i>Hahnia clathrata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
LYCOSIDAE	<i>Arctosa promontorii</i> (Purcell, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Hippasa funerea</i> Lessert, 1925	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna bimaculata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa biampliata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa bruneipes</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pterartoria subcrucifera</i> (Purcell, 1903)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
OXYOPIIDAE	<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes morpho</i> sp. 3 (new) (Fig. 10)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes russoi</i> Caporiacco, 1940	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes vogelsangeri</i> Lessert, 1946	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. immature		NE	
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
PHILODROMIDAE	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE
	New genus n. sp. (Fig. 9)		NE	
	<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
PHYXELIDIDAE	<i>Namaquarachne tropata</i> Griswold, 1990	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
PISAURIDAE	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Chiasmopes namaquensis</i> (Roewer, 1955)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Euprosthensopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Nilus massajae</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
SALTICIDAE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus capensis</i> Wesolowska, 1986	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus capicola</i> Simon, 1901	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus claviger</i> Simon, 1901	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus insperatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus peckhami</i> Simon, 1902	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Myrmarachne</i> sp. immature		NE	
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oviballus vidae</i> Azarkina & Haddad, 2020	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Pseudicius africanus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes modicus</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	1	LC	AE
<i>Rhene capensis</i> Strand, 1909 (Fig. 26)	5	DD	SAE	

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Thyene bucculenta</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873) (Fig. 25)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes cedri</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
SELENOPIDAE	<i>Anyphops atomarius</i> (Simon, 1887)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops</i> sp. immature		NE	
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Olios chelififer</i> Lawrence, 1937	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Parapalystes lycosinus</i> (Pocock, 1900)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Parapalystes megacephalus</i> (C.L. Koch, 1845)	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Parapalystes</i> cf. <i>whiteae</i> (Pocock, 1902)		NE	
STASIMOPIDAE	<i>Stasimopus brevipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	5	DD	SAE
TETRAGNATHIDAE	<i>Leucauge auronotum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tetragnatha demissa</i> L. Koch, 1872	0	LC	C
THERAPHOSIDAE	<i>Harpactira cafreriana</i> (Walckenaer, 1837)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Harpactira namaquensis</i> Purcell, 1902	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Harpactirella domicola</i> Purcell, 1903	5	LC	SAE
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Argyrodes argyroides</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	0	LC	C
	<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Phoroncidia capensis</i> (Simon, 1895)	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Ruborridion</i> n.sp. (Fig. 12)		NE	
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	Theridiidae sp. 1 cf. <i>Spinembolia</i> (Fig. 11)		NE	
	Theridiidae sp. 2 cf. <i>Macaridion</i>		NE	
	Theridiidae sp. 3 cf. <i>Dipoenura</i>		NE	
	Theridiidae sp. 4 cf. <i>Theridion</i>		NE	
THOMISIDAE	<i>Camarius nigrotesselatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Diaea albicincta</i> Pavesi, 1883	1	LC	AE
	<i>Holopelus almia</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1986	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> Lucas, 1864	0	LC	C
	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Phaenopoma nigropunctatum</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1883) (Fig. 24)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Pherecydes tuberculatus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1883	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Phrynarachne melloleitaoi</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema marlothi</i> Dahl, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Synema riflense</i> Strand, 1909	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus dalmasi</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE
TRACHELIDAE	<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Chariobas cylindraceus</i> Simon, 1893	1	LC	AE
	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Cicynethus mossambicus</i> Jocqué & Henrard, 2018	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Diores dowsetti</i> Jocqué, 1990	5	EN	SAE
ZOROPSIDAE	<i>Phanotea digitata</i> Griswold, 1994	5	LC	SAE

A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Benfontein Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape province, South Africa

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ABSTRACT: The aim of this study was to compile the first checklist of the spider species in the Northern Cape province at the Benfontein Nature Reserve. Spiders were collected during different survey periods using different collecting methods to sample both the ground and field layers. In total, 36 families represented by 112 genera and 167 species have been collected so far. The most species-rich families are the Gnaphosidae (35 spp.) and Salticidae (21 spp.), followed by the Lycosidae (11 spp.) and Araneidae (11 spp.), while 10 families are represented by singletons. Information on endemism value and conservation status are provided. Most of the species (92.2%) in the Benfontein Nature Reserve have a wide distribution with no known threats, with eight species that are data deficient and five were not evaluated. A large number of species (40.7%) are known throughout Southern Africa, while 21.6% of the species found in the reserve are African endemics, 49 spp. (29.3%) are South African endemics, and only four species (2.4%) are Northern Cape endemics.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, red list, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) collates species distribution data that are essential information needed for the conservation assessments when compiling a Red Data List (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015; Foord *et al.*, 2020). Survey data are needed to obtain species-specific information, and to determine new, rare, and/or endemic species and resources that are already in place in existing protected areas. The publication of these species checklists formed the basis of the first spider atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). The data are also used by the different provinces in their biodiversity assessments and action plans.

In South Africa, although the Northern Cape is the largest province (29.7%), it is still one of the poorest-sampled provinces, with only 490 spp. represented by 49 families known (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Several surveys have been conducted in the province but only a few checklists have been published such as spider diversity in pistachio orchards in the arid Northern Cape at Prieska (Haddad *et al.*, 2004, 2005, 2008; Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005); spiders from the Tswalu Kalahari Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018), and the Au-grabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

The current study presents the results of SANSA sampling and by-catch sampling in the Benfontein Nature Reserve on the border of the Northern Cape and Free State. Benfontein Nature Reserve (BNR) forms part of the Diamond Route Reserves, a set of sites across South Africa that conserve biodiversity and provide education and sustainability opportunities through the De Beers Group of Companies, E. Oppenheimer and Son and Ponahalo Investments. It is currently being managed as a nature reserve. Information on spider guilds, their habitat preference, and endemism index and conservation status are provided.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: BNR (-28.841, 24.851) is situated 14 km south-east of Kimberley and consists of flat plains on the central South African plateau at an altitude of about 1 180 m.a.s.l. with an area covering 11 000 ha (Figs 1 & 2).

It consists of a large calcrete pan (300 ha in size and c. 6 km in length) in the north-west that fills with water during good rains, creating a fertile shallow wetland. Specialised salt-tolerant plant communities surround the pan and two prominent drainage lines flow into it from the east. Away from the pan, the ground levels off and red Kalahari sand occurs to the south-east.

BNR is located in a transitional zone where Karoo, grassland and Kalahari thornveld savannah meet. The vegetation is mostly semi-open savanna of the Savanna Biome, with the Nama Karoo Biome present around the pan. There are three vegetation types: Highveld Salt Pans, Northern Upper Karoo, and Kimberley Thornveld. In the Kimberley Thornveld, the vegetation is generally open camel thorn *Vachellia erioloba* savanna in tall grass on deep red sands. The grass layer is complex and is dominated by *Eragrostis* species, silky grasses *Stipagrostis* species and stick grasses *Aristida* species. After good rains the flat country in the east becomes grassy, with red grass *Themeda triandra* and turpentine grass *Cymbopogon plurinodis* dominating.

Figure 1. Benfontein Nature Reserve

FIGURE 2: Map showing the location of the locality of the Benfontein Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape province.

Sampling method and period: Different surveys were undertaken over several years (1981–2018) (Table 1). The main focus was ground fauna sampling using pitfall traps. Identification was done by both authors. All the sampled material were deposited as voucher specimens at the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Only the generic names were included in the checklist when immature specimens were sampled and where some families lack taxonomic research to make species level identifications impossible.

TABLE 1: Surveys undertaken at the Benfontein Nature Reserve.

SURVEY TEAM	SAMPLING PROTOCOL	DATE
S. Erasmus (student)	Pitfall traps by-catch termite survey (by-catch)	1981 (12 months)
F. Dalerum	Pitfall traps sampling (by-catch)	2006–2011
C. Haddad	ad hoc sampling	2010
H. Badenhorst (student)	Pitfall traps sampling	2018

Endemicity value: The global distribution of species was used to determine the endemicity value of each species (Table 3).

Values used to indicate species endemicity (E):

- 6 – only known from the type locality (BNR);
- 5 – known from several localities in the Northern Cape (NCE);
- 4 – known from Northern Cape as well as a adjacent provinces;
- 3 – known from more than two provinces in South Africa (SAE);
- 2 – known from other Southern African countries (STHE);
- 1 – known from other countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE)
- 0 – also from countries outside the Afrotropical Region (CE).

Conservation status: The conservation status of each species was derived from a recent National Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020) where spatial analysis on observed occurrences using functions for Extent of Occurrence (EOO), Area of Occupancy (AOO), and elevational range the area of occupation was determined. The assumed knowledge of the full range for all species based on their observed occurrences, and EOO was calculated as the minimum convex polygon around all occurrences, and the 2 km² cells occupied were used to calculate AOO.

The distribution of threats across lineages was visualized using a mosaic plot, with the size of rectangles representing the proportion of species in a specific family represented within four categories: data deficient (DD), least concern (LC), rare, and threatened (Foord *et al.*, 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 167 species in 112 genera and 36 families were recorded (Tables 2 & 4). With the high number of pitfall traps used, the family Gnaphosidae was the most diverse family, with 35 species sampled, followed by the Salticidae with 21 species, and Araneidae and Lycosidae (11 spp.) (Table 2). Ten of the families are known only from a single species.

It compares well with the diversity of Tswalu Kalahari Reserve where 32 families represented by 108 genera and 136 species have been collected so far (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018).

TABLE 2: The spider families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.) sampled at the Benfontein Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape, South Africa.

FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	FAMILY	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	3	4	Oxyopidae	2	3
Araneidae	8	11	Palpimanidae	2	2
Caponiidae	1	1	Philodromidae	5	5
Cheiracanthiidae	1	2	Pholcidae	2	4
Corinnidae	3	3	Phyxelididae	1	1
Ctenidae	1	1	Pisauridae	2	2
Cyrtoucheniidae	1	4	Prodidomidae	2	3
Dictynidae	1	1	Salticidae	10	21
Eresidae	3	4	Scytodidae	1	2
Gallieniellidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	14	35	Sicariidae	2	2
Hersiliidae	1	1	Sparassidae	2	2
Idiopidae	2	2	Theraphosidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	2	2	Theridiidae	5	7
Lycosidae	8	11	Thomisidae	8	9
Oecobiidae	1	1	Trachelidae	4	4
Oonopidae	4	5	Zodariidae	5	7
Orsolobidae	1	1	36	112	167

Conservation status: Most of the species 154 (92.2%) have a wide distribution range and are listed as Least Concern while eight species are Data Deficient, lacking distribution or taxonomic resolution (Table 3). Species of the three genera (*Castianeira*, *Dictyna*, and *Orchestina*) still lack taxonomic resolution and five were not evaluated. The Orsolobidae species sampled is possibly new to science (Table 4).

Species endemicity: A large percentage of species (36 spp., 21.6%) have a wide distribution throughout Africa, while 9 spp. (5.3%) are also found wider than Africa. A total of 68 spp. (40.7%) are endemics to Southern Africa and 49 spp. (29.3%) are South African endemics.

The following four species are endemic to the Northern Cape (Table 4): *Ancylotrypa namaquensis* Purcell, 1908), *A. pusilla* (Purcell, 1903) (Cyrtoucheniidae), *Cydrela friedlanderae* Hewitt, 1914, and *Cyrioctea lotzi* Jocqué, 2013 (Zodariidae), while *Opopaea gaborone* Saaristo & Marusik, 2008 (Oonopidae) is for the first time reported from South Africa. BNR is the type locality of *Austrachelas kalaharinus* Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009.

TABLE 3: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at Benfontein Nature Reserve.

CONSERVATION STATUS	SPP.	CODE	%
Data deficient (taxonomic reason or lack distribution data)	8	DD	4.8
Not evaluated (immature, new or undetermined)	5	NE	2.9
Least concern	154	LC	92.2
ENDEMICITY			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	9	LC	5.3
1 – African endemics (AE)	36	LC	21.6
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	68	LC	40.7
3 – South African endemics (SAE): More than three provinces	31	LC	18.6
4 – South African endemics (SAE): Two adjacent provinces	14	DD/LC	8.3
5 – Northern Cape endemics (NCE)	4	DD/LC	2.4
6 – Known only from type locality	0		0

CONCLUSION

This survey forms part of the SANSa survey for the Northern Cape province and, as such, represents new distribution records for 167 species. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research. Established reserves, such as BNR, can make a substantial contribution towards invertebrate conservation. However, the contribution of existing reserves can only be highlighted through studies such as this.

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Figures 3–17. Spiders from Benfontein Nature Reserve. **Caponiidae**: 3. *Caponia capensis*. **Cyrtachenidae**: 4. *Ancylotrypa pusilla*. 5. *Ancylotrypa pretoriae*. **Eresidae**: 6. *Seothyra fasciata*. **Araneidae**: 7. *Kilima decens*. **Eresidae**: 8. *Gandanameno spenceri*. **Gnaphosidae**: 9. *Ammoxenus coccineus*. 10. *Asemesthes oconnori*. 11. *Drassodes lophognathus*. 12. *Nomisia varia*. **Hersiliidae**: 13. *Tyrotama australis*. **Lycosidae**: 14. *Evippomma squamulatum*. 15. *Hogna schreineri*. **Philodromidae**: 16. *Hirriusa arenacea*. **Palpimanidae**: 17. *Diaphorocellus biplagiatus*. Photos: Peter Webb.

Figures 18–32. Spiders from Benfontein Nature Reserve. **Salticidae**: 18. *Baryphas ahenus*. 19. *Heliophanus pistaciae*. 20. *Natta chionogaster*. 21. *Pellenes bulawayoensis*. **Pisauridae**: 22. *Rothus aethiopicus*. **Prodidomidae**: 23. *Theuma foveolate*. **Sicariidae**: 24. *Hexophthalma hahni*. **Sparassidae**: 25. *Arandisa deserticola*. 26. *Eusparassus schoemanae*. **Thomisidae**: 27. *Pherecydes tuberculatus*. 28. *Thomisus stenningi*. 29. *Stiphropus affinis*. **Trachelidae**: 30. *Orthobula arca*. **Zodariidae**: 31. *Diores poweri*. 32. *Heradida loricata*. Photos: Peter Webb.

TABLE 4. Checklist of the spiders species recorded from the Benfontein Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape with information on their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEND) and provincial endemics (PROVE). * possibly new species or new record.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
AGELENIDAE	<i>Agelena australis</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
	<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Benoitia deserticola</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Mistaria zuluana</i> (Roewer, 1955)	2	LC	STHE
ARANEIDAE	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866) (Fig. 7)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinia natalensis</i> (Grasshoff, 1971)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	0	LC	C
	<i>Zygiella x-notata</i> (Clerck, 1757)	0	LC	C
CAPONIIDAE	<i>Caponia capensis</i> Purcell, 1904 (Fig. 3)	2	LC	STHE
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	<i>Cheiramiona ferrumfontis</i> Lotz, 2002	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona boschrandensis</i> Lotz, 2015	4	DD	SAE
CORINNIDAE	<i>Castianeira</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
	<i>Copuetta lotzi</i> Haddad, 2013	3	LC	SAE
CTENIDAE	<i>Ctenus spectabilis</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	<i>Ancylotrypa namaquensis</i> (Purcell, 1908)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Ancylotrypa pusilla</i> (Purcell, 1903) (Fig. 4)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913) (Fig. 5)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ancylotrypa sororum</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.(undetermined)		NE	
ERESIDAE	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900) (Fig. 8)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Paradonea parva</i> (Tucker, 1920)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Paradonea splendens</i> (Lawrence, 1936)	3	DD	SAE
	<i>Seothyra fasciata</i> Purcell, 1904 (Fig. 6)	2	LC	STHE
GALLIENIELLIDAE	<i>Austrachelas kalaharinus</i> Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009 HT*	4	DD	SAE
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Ammoxenus coccineus</i> Simon, 1893 (Fig. 9)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Aneplasa nigra</i> Tucker, 1923	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes lineatus</i> Purcell, 1908	1	LC	AE
	<i>Asemesthes montanus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes oconnori</i> Tucker, 1923 (Fig. 10)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes paynteri</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Camillina maun</i> Platnick & Murphy, 1987	1	LC	AE
	<i>Drassodes ereptor</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Drassodes lophognathus</i> Purcell, 1907(Fig. 11)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Drassodes solitarius</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Echemus erutus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Ibala bilinearis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Ibala bulawayensis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Megamyrmaekion schreineri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Megamyrmaekion transvaalense</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> Tucker, 1923	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923) (Fig.12)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rastellus deserticola</i> Haddad, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Setaphis browni</i> (Tucker, 1923)	0	LC	C
	<i>Xerophaeus aridus</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Xerophaeus lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus spoliator</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Xerophaeus spiralifer</i> Purcell, 1907	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus vickermani</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes tuckeri</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
HERSILIIDAE	<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893) (Fig. 13)	2	LC	STHE
IDIOPIDAE	<i>Gorgyrella schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Idiops pullus</i> Tucker, 1917	4	LC	SAE
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE
LYCOSIDAE	<i>Allocosa aurichelis</i> Roewer, 1959	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898) (Fig. 14)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898) (Fig. 15)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Lycosa rimicola</i> Purcell, 1903	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa injucunda</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Tricassa deserticola</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zenonina mystacina</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
OECOBIIDAE	<i>Uroctea quinquenotata</i> Simon, 1910	4	LC	SAE
OONOPIIDAE	<i>Dysderina speculifera</i> Simon, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Gamasomorpha humicola</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Opopaea speciosa</i> (Lawrence, 1952)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Opopaea gaborone</i> Saaristo & Marusik, 2008	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Orchestina</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
ORSOLOBIDAE	<i>Afrilobus</i> possible new sp.		NE	
OXYOPIIDAE	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Peucetia viridis</i> (Blackwall, 1858)	1	LC	AE
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Diaphorocellus biplagiatus</i> Simon, 1893	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Palpimanus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910 (Fig. 17)	2	LC	STHE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Philodromidae	<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927) (Fig. 16)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana</i> sp. immature		NE	
	<i>Smeringopus koppies</i> Huber, 2012	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Hubert, 2012	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
Phyxelididae	<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE
Pisauridae	<i>Cispus kimbis</i> Blandin, 1978	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883) (Fig. 22)	1	LC	AE
Prodidomidae	<i>Austrodomus scaber</i> (Purcell, 1904)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma foveolata</i> Tucker, 1923 (Fig. 23)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma maculata</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
Salticidae	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902 (Fig. 18)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003 (Fig. 19)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus prozyskii</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus termitophagus</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2002	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Icius insolitus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901) (Fig. 20)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000 (Fig. 21)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pellenes modicus</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2007	3	LC	STHE
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Psenec dependens</i> (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	
Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes arenacea</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Scytodes broomi</i> Pocock, 1902	4	DD	SAE
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna karrooica</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops barnardi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	2	LC	STHE
Sicariidae	<i>Hexophthalma hahni</i> (Karsch, 1878) (Fig. 24)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
Sparassidae	<i>Arandisa deserticola</i> Lawrence, 1938 (Fig. 25)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Eusparassus schoemanae</i> Moradmand, 2013 (Fig. 26)	2	LC	STHE
Theraphosidae	<i>Idiothele nigrofulva</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
Theridiidae	<i>Enoplognatha inornata</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
PHILODROMIDAE	<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
PHOLCIDAE	<i>Quamtana</i> sp. immature		NE	
	<i>Smeringopus koppies</i> Huber, 2012	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Hubert, 2012	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
PHYXELIDIDAE	<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE
PISAURIDAE	<i>Cispus kimbius</i> Blandin, 1978	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
PRODIDOMIDAE	<i>Austrodomus scaber</i> (Purcell, 1904)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma foveolata</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma maculata</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
SALTICIDAE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus proszynskii</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus termitophagus</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2002	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pellenes modicus</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2007	3	LC	STHE
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Psenuc dependens</i> (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes arenacea</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Scytodes broomi</i> Pocock, 1902	4	DD	SAE
SEGESTRIIDAE	<i>Ariadna karrooica</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
SELENOPIDAE	<i>Anyphops barnardi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	2	LC	STHE
SICARIIDAE	<i>Hexophthalma hahni</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Arandisa deserticola</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Eusparassus schoemanae</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE
THERAPHOSIDAE	<i>Idiothele nigrofulva</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Enoplognatha inornata</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
THOMISIDAE	<i>Phoroncidia eburnea</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Heriaeus allenjonesi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> Lucas, 1864	0	LC	C
	<i>Ozyptila caenosa</i> Jézéquel, 1966	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pherecydes tuberculatus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1883 (Fig. 27)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Simorcus lotzi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Stiphropus affinis</i> Lessert, 1923 (Fig. 29)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE
TRACHELIDAE	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900 (Fig. 28)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Afroceto africana</i> (Simon 1910)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Fuchibotulus kigelia</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Orthobula arca</i> Haddad, Jin & Platnick, 2022 (Fig. 30)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Poachelas striatus</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	3	LC	SAE
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Cydrela friedlanderae</i> Hewitt, 1914	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Cydrela spinifrons</i> Hewitt, 1915	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Cyrioctea lotzi</i> Jocqué, 2013	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920 (Fig. 31)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Diores triangulifer</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heradida loricata</i> Simon, 1893 (Fig. 32)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Ranops caprivi</i> Jocqué, 1991	2	LC	STHE

A review of the synanthropic spiders from South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: Spiders are frequently encountered in houses and outbuildings in South Africa. With the warm subtropical climate, houses, windows, and security doors are frequently left open, allowing spiders to enter freely. Data for this review were obtained from museum databases and primary specimen data were collected with specimens and extracted from published revisions. A total of 86 synanthropic species from 22 spider families have so far been recorded from buildings in South Africa, of which 17 species are hemisynanthropic and 56 are asynanthropic species that are accidentally recorded from buildings but only 13 species are eusynanthropic species living exclusively in buildings. Many of the species regularly found associated with buildings are introduced species.

Key notes: alien species, asynanthropic, eusynanthropic, hemisynanthropic, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

Information on spiders in urban areas has increased in the last 20 years, especially in Europe and North America. A number of publications deal with synanthropic spiders (Cutler, 1973; Kaston, 1983; Taucare-Ríos *et al.*, 2013) but many focused on species that live in man-made habitats like gardens and crops, and not especially in houses. Only a few studies restricted the observations to spiders found in houses. Smithers (1990) recorded house spiders in the Plymouth area (UK), Guarisco (1999) studied these animals in Kansas (USA), Armas (2003) provided an account of spiders in a house in Cuba, and Jocqué *et al.* (2016) in Belgium. From Africa the first information on synanthropic species was provided by Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), data have been collected on species distribution in urban areas. With the introduction of the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and the Spider Identification Service at the Agricultural Research Council, National Collection of Arachnida (NCA), we obtained information on synanthropic species in South Africa.

More than 10 000 records of spiders recorded from buildings were extracted from databases based on primary data collected with specimens housed in natural history collections of the NCA and the National Museum in Bloemfontein. The checklist (Table 1) includes references to taxonomic papers of species confirming their presence in houses and on the outside of houses.

Spiders associated with houses and outbuildings can be conveniently divided into three categories, according to Rozwałka (2006):

Eusynanthropic species (ES) – species living exclusively in man-made areas. They are true synanthropes associated with houses, where they live and breed. Many of the species have very wide global distributions because they are often accidentally transported to new areas. They seldom occur locally in the natural environment.

Hemisynanthropic species (HS) – species commonly found in synanthropic environments, although they often occur in natural environments as well. It includes species that are seasonally abundant in natural habitats and in houses. Although some may hibernate indoors, and the emergence of large numbers of spiderlings from an occasional egg sac may give the impression of an infestation, these species do not establish populations inside houses.

Asynanthropic species (AS) – spiders occurring in natural conditions, and they are only accidentally found in buildings.

In this paper we present a checklist of spider families and species associated with buildings in South Africa.

Figure 1. *Selenops radiatus* Latreille, 1819, a eusynanthropic species commonly found in houses in some provinces of South Africa. Photo: Peter Webb.

Figure 2. *Oecobius navus* Blackwall, 1859, a eusynanthropic species found throughout South Africa in houses. Photo: Peter Webb.

RESULTS

A total of 22 spider families and 82 species have been recorded from buildings in South Africa. Most of the species (54) are asynanthropic species and are only accidentally found in synanthropic environments. Several species (15) are hemisynanthropic species that spend some time in a synanthropic environment, but they are found in natural conditions as well. Only a few species (13) are eusynanthropic and in South Africa they are exclusively associated with buildings.

Of the 2 253 species of spiders presently recorded from South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020), 74 species are cosmopolitan or introduced. Introductions of species beyond their natural range are rising because of the increasing trade, transport, travel, and tourism connected to globalisation.

Species from the following families have been recorded:

1. AGELENIDAE

Three introduced species of the genus *Tegenaria* are synanthropic and found in buildings in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997). Lawrence (1964) was the first to report that *Tegenaria* spp. are occasionally found in houses in Cape Town. The three introduced species (Table 1) were recorded in and around outbuildings in the Gauteng, Mpumalanga, Eastern Cape, and Western Cape provinces of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021a).

2. ARANEIDAE

A large number of araneid species are commonly found in gardens but only single species are sometimes accidentally carried into houses but that is very rare. It is mainly the cosmopolitan hermit spider *Nephilingis cruentata* (Fabricius, 1775) that make their large orb-web spider with a funnel retreat under the overhang of roofs in Limpopo, Mpumalanga, and KwaZulu-Natal (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014, 2023; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022b).

3. CHEIRACANTHIDAE

The genus *Cheiracanthium* was revised by Lotz (1995, 2007) and it is mainly the African endemic species *C. furculatum* Karsch, 1879 that are commonly found in house throughout South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2017; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021b; 2021f). During the day they are found in a soft silk retreats usually made in folds of fabric or in the corners of walls and ceilings, but at night they wander around in search of food and then land in beds and, when threatened, they may administer bites (Newlands, 1975, 1976, 1977, 1978).

4. CLUBIONIDAE

Clubionids are free-living, nocturnal hunters commonly found on vegetation. They make sac-like retreats in rolled-up vegetation and grasses. The genus was revised by Mbo (2022) and he reports two species that have been sampled from houses in Bloemfontein and Pretoria.

5. DEINOPIDAE

Menneus camelus Pocock, 1902, a South African endemic species, catch moths with expandable webs and were frequently encountered in houses, usually in bathrooms in South Africa, as reported by Coddington *et al.* (2012); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2020a).

6. DESIDAE

Badumna longinqua L. Koch, 1867, a species native to Australia, make cribellate webs between leaves and hollow areas, and are commonly found around houses (Fig. 3). Only one species has recently been introduced into South Africa, where it constructs webs on walls and roofs (Haddad, 2011, 2012; Haddad & Foord, 2021).

Badumna longinqua has been sampled from the southern coastal areas (Eastern and Western Cape provinces) and central Free State province, with almost all of the records associated with synanthropic urban habitats (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021c).

Figure 3. *Badumna longinqua*. a. Female b. Retreats on roof. Photos: C. Haddad.

7. DICTYNIDAE

Brigittea civica (Lucas, 1850), an introduced species (Fig. 4c), was discovered for the first time in Pretoria in 2011 (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2012a; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020c). It is a web dweller that makes retreat-webs on walls (Fig. 4b). The spider takes up position in the middle of the web and the web consists of sticky threads radiating outwards (Fig. 4a). They made quite a mess on a building at Roodeplaat (Fig. 4b).

Figures 4 a-c. *Brigittea civica* with webs. Photos: P. Webb.

8. DRYMUSIDAE

Izithunzi capense (Simon, 1893) is a Western Cape endemic species that usually hangs beneath loose space webs and are found hidden in wall crevices or below leaf litter and has been reported to wander inside houses in Cape Town (iNaturalist).

9. DYSDERIDAE

Dysdera crocata C.L. Koch, 1838 is a cosmopolitan species that is often associated with human habitations (Cooke, 1965). Although *D. crocata* has been introduced into most countries worldwide and often encountered in and around houses, it is not widespread in the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa it has been found in houses in the Western Cape and Gauteng (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020b).

10. FILISTATIDAE

Filistatids are nocturnal spiders, living in tubular silk-lined retreats in crevices in rocks or walls. The species *Andoharano ansieae* Zonstein & Marusik, 2015 was for the first time recorded from houses in Gravelotte and Hoedspruit in the eastern part of Limpopo

(Eichhoff *et al.*, 2021; Figure 5. *Andoharano ansieae*. Photo: A. Eichhoff.

11. GNAPHOSIDAE

The Gnaphosidae is a large family of ground dwellers and only a few gnaphosid species are known to share human habitations. Two synanthropic species, *Marinarozelotes jaxartensis* (Kroneberg, 1875) and *Urozelotes rusticus* (L. Koch, 1872), have been transported by humans to many parts of the world, occurring in houses and disturbed habitats in regions with warm climates (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021d). In a recent revision of *Afrodrassex* (Haddad & Booysen, 2022), the majority of the specimens of the species *A. balrog* Haddad & Booysen, 2022 were collected inside houses and gardens in central South Africa at night.

12. MITURGIDAE

Specimens of *Parapostenus* have been sampled from Hogsback but the taxonomy of the genus is still unresolved (Haddad *et al.*, in press).

13. OECOBIIDAE

Several species of *Oecobius* are synanthropic and two cosmopolitan species, *O. navus* Blackwall, 1859 (Fig. 2) and *O. putus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 (Fig. 6), are known from the Afrotropical Region and South Africa. *Oecobius navus* has the widest distribution and is found throughout South Africa, associated with buildings (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021e, 2022b).

Figure 6. *Oecobius putus*. Photo: R. Steenkamp

14. OONOPIDAE

Some oonopids are found in association with dry material, for example in hay-sheds and bird nests. They even occur in dry insect collections where they probably prey on *Acarus* mites. In South Africa, the African endemic species *Opopaea speciosa* (Lawrence, 1952) has been sampled from thatched roofs in Mpumalanga, where they were present in large numbers dropping down on the furniture (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997).

15. PHOLCIDAE

Pholcids are commonly found in human habitations and several species have been recorded from South Africa. *Artema atlanta* Walckenaer, 1837 occurs throughout Africa (Huber, 2003) and the species has been reported from localities in the Northern Cape and Mpumalanga (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). *Crossopriza lyoni* (Blackwall, 1867), a cosmopolitan species, was the first time reported from South Africa by Huber (2003) (Fig. 7a). It has since been recorded from Pretoria (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009), where they were present in high numbers covering the walls and ceiling with their webbing (Fig. 7b). *Smeringopus natalensis* Lawrence, 1947 and *S. lotzi* Huber, 2012 are common species sampled from houses in South Africa (Huber, 2012; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014, 2023).

Figures 7. *Crossopriza lyoni*. a. Female. b. Webbing Photos: P. Marais.

16. PISAURIDAE

Pisaurid species are commonly found in gardens and some of the species sometimes wander into residences, e.g. *Rothus aethiopicus* (Pavesi, 1883). Jones (2016) reported on a female *Euprosphenops australis* Simon, 1898 breeding in a house in the Free State. A species regularly recorded from houses in that province.

17. SALTICIDAE

Salticids are commonly found in gardens and possibly most of the 23 species reported from buildings are accidental visitors. Only the cosmopolitan species such as *Hasarius adansoni* (Audouin, 1826) and *Menemerus bivittatus* Dufour, 1831 are frequently encountered in houses and other buildings (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014, 2023).

18. SCYTODIDAE

Two cosmopolitan species, *Scytodes fusca* Walckenaer 1837 and *S. thoracica* Latreille 1802, are mentioned in the literature to occur in houses (Lawrence, 1964; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021g). However, in a revision of *Scytodes* presently under way (Booyesen [pers.com]), only *S. elizabethae* Purcell, 1904 and *S. univittata* Simon, 1882 are frequently associated with buildings in South Africa.

19. SELENOPIIDAE

Nine selenopid species have been identified as synanthropic and are among the most common spiders encountered on walls in South Africa. When disturbed they disappear under wall hangings or into crevices. Their round, flat, papery egg-sacs are frequently seen on wooden beams (Croeser, 1979). Visser (1993a,b) reported on the occurrence of *Selenops radiatus* Latreille, 1819 in potato sheds in South Africa where it preys on the potato tuber moth, cockroaches, and silverfish (Corronco, 2002; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997, Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020e).

20. SICARIIDAE

Loxosceles spp. are not web-bound spiders and spin only a few irregular strands of silk that serve as retreats made under objects on the ground or in dark corners in buildings, outbuildings, and caves (Newlands, 1975). Four *Loxosceles* species have been recorded from buildings: *L. dejagerae* Lotz, 2017, *L. simillima* Lawrence, 1927, *L. spinulosa* Purcell, 1904, and *L. parramae* Newlands, 1981 (Fig. 8.). In some houses in Bloemfontein *L. simillima* is frequently found in houses. (Newlands, 1980; Lotz, 2012 & 2017; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021h).

Figure 8. *Loxosceles parramae* from Kempton Park. Photo: W. Schmidt.

21. SPARASSIDAE

In the Sparassidae it is mainly *Palystes* spp. that are usually associated with buildings. From the revision of *Palystes* by Croeser (1996), seven species have been sampled from suburban gardens and buildings in Southern Africa. They are commonly known as rain spiders as they wander into houses during the rainy season. Two of the species are very commonly encountered in houses, namely *P. castaneus* (Latreille, 1819) in the southwestern Cape, particularly the Cape Peninsula, and *P. superciliosus* L. Koch, 1875 that occurs throughout South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022a).

22. THERIDIIDAE

Many theridiids are associated with buildings. The preferred web sites are usually on stone walls and crevices in house walls and window frames and seven species are listed in Table 1. The larger *Latrodectus* species are frequently encountered and the introduced *Latrodectus geometricus* C.L. Koch, 1841 is very commonly found in built-up areas, usually outside houses where they make their webs in dark areas such as under window sills and verandas. *Latrodectus renivulvatus* Dahl, 1902 is less common in built-up areas but specimens have been collected from inside houses in Gauteng (Lotz, 1994; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021d, e).

23. TRACHELIDAE

In the Trachelidae, three *Afrocto* species and two *Orthobula* species have been sampled from buildings. They are, however, synanthropic species that are only accidentally found in buildings (Lyle & Haddad, 2010; Haddad *et al.*, 2022).

24. TROCHANTERIIDAE

The Trochanteriidae species are free-living wanderers with flattened bodies, adapted to life in narrow crevices. *Platyoides walteri* Karsch, 1886, the most common species in Southern Africa, is synanthropic and frequently encountered in buildings, often found underneath plant containers on verandahs (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022c).

25. ULOBORIDAE

Several uloborid species have a cosmopolitan distribution and are frequently found in and around houses. The following species are recorded from the Afrotropical Region: *Uloborus plumipes* Lucas, 1846; *U. walckenaerius* Latreille, 1806, and *Zosis geniculata* Olivier (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997). In South Africa especially *Uloborus plumipes* is commonly found in buildings (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020f).

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TABLE 1. Spider species found in buildings in South Africa. ST status: ES eusynanthropic species; HS hemisynanthropic species; AS asynanthropic species. AD abundance R rare; c common; VC very common.

SPECIES	ST	AB	REFERENCES
1. AGELENIDAE			
<i>Tegenaria domestica</i> (Clerck, 1757)	ES	R	Lawrence (1964); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021a)
<i>Tegenaria pagana</i> C.L. Koch, 1840	ES	R	Le Roux & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2016)
<i>Tegenaria parietina</i> (Fourcroy, 1785)	ES	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021a)
2. ARANEIDAE			
<i>Nephilingis cruentata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	HS	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b); Holm & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2010)
3. CHEIRACANTHIIDAE			
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	HS	VC	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Lotz (1995, 2007); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz (2017); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021b, 2021f); Newlands (1975)
4. CLUBIONIDAE			
<i>Clubiona</i> (undescribed new sp.)	AS	R	Mbo (2022)
<i>Clubiona revillioidi</i> Lessert, 1936	AS	R	Mbo (2022)
5. DEINOPIIDAE			
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	AS	R	Coddington <i>et al.</i> (2012); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020a)
6. DESIDAE			
<i>Badumna longinqua</i> L. Koch, 1867	ES	C	Haddad (2011, 2012); Haddad & Foord (2021); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)
7. DICTYNIDAE			
<i>Brigittea civica</i> (Lucas, 1850)	ES	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2012a); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020c)
8. DRYMUSIDAE			
<i>Izithunzi capense</i> (Simon, 1893)	HS	R	Anecdotal, Spider Club face book
9. DYSDERIDAE			
<i>Dysdera crocata</i> C.L. Koch, 1838	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020b)
10. FILISTATIDAE			
<i>Andoharano ansieae</i> Zonstein & Marusik, 2015	HS	R	Eichhoff <i>et al.</i> (2021); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
11. GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Afrodrassex balrog</i> Haddad & Booysen, 2022	AS	C	Haddad & Booysen, 2022
<i>Marinarozelotes jaxartensis</i> (Kroneberg, 1875)	AS	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021d)
<i>Urozelotes rusticus</i> (L. Koch, 1872)	AS	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021d)
12. MITURGIDAE			
<i>Parapostenus</i> sp. (undetermined)	AS	R	Haddad <i>et al.</i> (2023) (Hogsback)
13. OECOBIIDAE			
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	ES	VC	Lawrence (1964); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021e, 2022b)
<i>Oecobius putus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021e, 2022b)
14. OONOPIIDAE			
<i>Opopaea speciosa</i> (Lawrence, 1952)	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997)
15. PHOLCIDAE			
<i>Artema atlanta</i> Walckenaer, 1837	HS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Huber (2003)
<i>Crossopriza lyoni</i> (Blackwall, 1867)	ES	R	Huber (2003; 2009); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2012)
<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Huber, 2012	HS	VC	Huber (2012); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014)
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	HS	VC	Holm & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2010); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014)
16. PISAURIDAE			
<i>Euprosthenoops australis</i> Simon, 1898	AS	R	Jones (2016); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020d)
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020d)
17. SALTICIDAE			
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	AS	C	Haddad & Wesotowska (2011)
<i>Evarcha ignea</i> Wesotowska & Cumming, 2008	AS	C	Wesotowska & Cumming (2008); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2023)
<i>Evarcha zimbabwensis</i> Wesotowska & Cumming, 2008	AS	C	Wesotowska & Cumming (2008)

SPECIES	ST	AB	REFERENCES
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> (Audouin, 1826)	HS	VC	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Heliophanus demonstrativus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	AS	R	Wesolowska (1986)
<i>Holcolaetis vellerea</i> Simon, 1909	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Heliophanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1901	AS	R	Haddad & Wesolowska (2011)
<i>Hyllus argyrotoxicus</i> Simon, 1902	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008); Wesolowska & Haddad (2009)
<i>Hyllus dotata</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Hyllus treleaveni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	AS	R	Wesolowska & Haddad (2009)
<i>Icius insolitus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Menemerus carlini</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Menemerus bifurcus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	AS	R	Wesolowska (1999)
<i>Menemerus bivittatus</i> Dufour, 1831	HS	VC	Lawrence (1942); Wesolowska (1999); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014)
<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	AS	R	Haddad & Wesolowska (2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014)
<i>Mexcala elegans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Wesolowska & Haddad (2009)
<i>Myrmarachne laurentina</i> Bacelar, 1953	AS	R	Wesolowska & Haddad (2009)
<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	AS	R	Lawrence (1942); Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Rumburak laxus</i> (Zhang & Maddison, 2012)	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2023)
<i>Rumburak mirabilis</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	AS	R	Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith (2014)
18. SCYTODIDAE			
<i>Scytodes fusca</i> Walckenaer 1837	ES	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021g)
<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904	ES	C	Booyens (<i>Scytodes</i> revision in progress)
<i>Scytodes univittata</i> Simon, 1882	ES	C	Booyens (<i>Scytodes</i> revision in progress)
19. SELENOPIIDAE			
<i>Anyphops capensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	AS	R	Corronco (2002); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Anyphops fitzsimonsi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	AS	R	Lawrence (1940); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Anyphops immaculatus</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	AS	R	Lawrence (1940); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Anyphops marshalli</i> (Pocock, 1902)	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Anyphops stauntoni</i> Benoit, 1968	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Selenops alticolus</i> Lawrence, 1940	AS	R	Corronco (2002); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Selenops krugeri</i> Lawrence, 1940	AS	R	Corronco (2002)
<i>Selenops tuckeri</i> Lawrence, 1940	AS	C	Lawrence (1940); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Selenops radiatus</i> Latreille, 1819	ES	C	Visser (1993a,b); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Corronco (2002)
20. SICARIIDAE			
<i>Loxosceles dejagerae</i> Lotz, 2017	AS	C	Lotz (2017)
<i>Loxosceles parramae</i> Newlands, 1981	ES	VC	Newlands (1975; 1980; 1981); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Lotz (2012; 2017); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	AS	VC	Newlands (1975; 1986); Lotz (2017)
<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	AS	VC	Newlands (1975); Lotz (2012; 2017)
21. SPARASSIDAE			
<i>Palystes castaneus</i> (Latreille, 1819)	AS	VC	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes karoensis</i> Croeser, 1996	AS	R	Croeser (1996)
<i>Palystes leppanae</i> Pocock, 1902	AS	C	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes leroyorum</i> Croeser, 1996	AS	R	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes perornatus</i> Pocock, 1900	AS	R	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes stuarti</i> Croeser, 1996	AS	R	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	HS	VC	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)

SPECIES	ST	AB	REFERENCES
22. THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	HS	VC	Lotz (1994); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz (2017)
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	HS	C	Lotz (1994); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz (2017)
<i>Parasteatoda tepidariorum</i> (C. L. Koch, 1841)	ES	VC	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022d)
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	HS	C	Hann (1990); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022e)
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1905	HS	VC	Lawrence (1964); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022e)
<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	HS	C	Knoflach & Harten van (2006); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022e)
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	AS	C	Anecdotal, attch webs to building
23. TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Afrocto africana</i> (Simon, 1910)	AS	R	Lyle & Haddad (2010)
<i>Afrocto corcula</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2010	AS	R	Lyle & Haddad (2010)
<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	AS	R	Lyle & Haddad (2010)
<i>Orthobula arca</i> Haddad, Jin & Platnick, 2022	AS	R	Haddad, Jin & Platnick (2022)
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897	AS	R	Haddad, Jin & Platnick (2022)
24. TROCHANTERIIDAE			
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> Karsch, 1886	HS	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023)
25. ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	HS	VC	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020f)
<i>Uloborus walckenaerius</i> Latreille, 1806	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020f)

Field Guide to the
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THE BOOK

Thoroughly revised and updated, this long-awaited new edition of *Field Guide to the Spiders of South Africa* remains the most comprehensive guide to South African spiders published to date. It features over 780 of the more common spider species encountered in the veld and in homes and gardens, as well as representative species from some of the rarer spider families.

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